

Assessing travel impacts of digital care: a case study report

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This case study report is an output of the study [“Environmental impacts of digital services for health and wellbeing in the home”](#).

A quantitative case study was developed as a worked example of a method for assessing the travel impacts of a digital healthcare intervention. For this quantitative exercise, we worked with an NHS Trust in southern England, in a largely rural area. We focused on care provided to patients with a specific chronic (long term) health condition, who were offered the option of online/phone consultations. No personal data about patients (e.g. age, gender) was used in this case study, for ethical reasons. We used data on the number and type of consultations for 331 patients over three months in 2022. The dataset provided information on whether each patient travelled to a hospital or opted for online/phone consultations in that period (after a visit to a GP for blood testing). Practitioners within the NHS Trust also calculated how far each patient travelled and provided this as anonymised data.

Among the 331 patients in the study, there were a total of 430 consultations, with 326 of them conducted online/ by phone. Patients travelled on average 13.9 km (combined for GP and hospital consultations).

To understand the potential for CO₂ eq. reduction through digital consultations, our first step was to develop two scenarios in consultation with the Trust practitioners.

“Only online”: in this scenario, all patients opt exclusively for online/phone consultations instead of hospital consultations. However, this “Only online” scenario still requires patients to travel to their GP practice for blood testing.

“Only in-person”: in this scenario, all patients opt exclusively for in-person consultations at the nearest hospital.

We present results regarding travel distances for the current care situation and the two scenarios in Table 4. The distribution of the distances travelled by the 331 patients in the current situation and the two scenarios is shown in the boxplot (Figure 1).

Table 4 - Current travel for patients in the dataset (current care situation), and the estimated “only online” and “only in person” scenarios for the 331 patients during the three months.

	Current care situation	“Only online” scenario	“Only in-person” scenario
Number of online / phone appointments	326	430	0
Number of hospital appointments	104	0	430
Total distance travelled (km)	4,601	2,215	12,171
Average distance travelled by a patient (km)	13.9	6.7	36.7

Figure 1 - Boxplot showing the distribution of the distances travelled by the 331 patients. The interquartile range is depicted by the box, which spans from the first quartile to the third quartile of the dataset and encompasses the middle 50% of the data. The median value is represented by the line within the box and the average by the “x”. The whiskers extending from the box indicate the minimum and maximum values within 1.5 times the interquartile range. Data points outside the whiskers are considered outliers and represented as dots (these likely denote the patients who live furthest from health facilities).

As Figure 1 shows, the only online scenario involves considerably less travel per patient than the other scenarios.

Based on these findings, the next step was to estimate potential CO₂ eq. impacts of the different scenarios. This meant adopting assumptions about typical modes of travel, and the carbon footprint of these modes. We used CO₂ eq. emissions factors per km for different modes of travel (shown in Table 4). Figures for the share of travel by different modes are from the UK’s Department of Transport, and the percentage of petrol, diesel and electric cars estimated from statistics for the year 2019 (Society of Motor Manufacturers and Traders, 2023; UK Department of Transport, 2023a) (“Current travel situation” in Table 4). Figures for CO₂ eq. per km are estimated from (Huijbregts et al., 2017; Wernet et al., 2016). As the UK plans to ban the sale of internal combustion cars (petrol, diesel and hybrid vehicles) by 2030 (UK Department of Transport, 2023b), we evaluated another scenario based on this commitment to total

electrification of road transport. This scenario assumes 100% adoption of electric cars (“Full electric cars” scenario in Table 4) and maintains the same proportions of travel modes and CO₂ eq. emissions per km.

Table 5 – Present travel modes (%) in England for the “Current travel situation” and “Full electric cars” scenario, and their respective CO₂ eq. emission factors.

Mode of travel	% of travel		kg CO ₂ eq. per km*
	Current travel situation	“Full electric cars” scenario	
Walk / bicycle	3.0	3.0	0.0000
Bus	6.0	6.0	0.0996
Car (petrol)	54.0	0.0	0.2680
Car (diesel)	30.4	0.0	0.2360
Car (hybrid)**	1.3	0.0	0.2433
Car (electric)	1.3	87.0	0.2260
Train/underground***	4.0	4.0	0.0164

*Estimates are for the European fleet before 2021 and may differ for the UK.
 ** Average from petrol, diesel and electric cars. ***Assumed similar to a tram.

We took these factors from Table 5, and applied them to the average distances travelled by a patient shown in Table 4 (13.9 km, 6.7 km and 36.7 km for the current care situation, “only online” and “only in-person” scenarios respectively). This meant we could estimate the CO₂ eq. impacts of patient travel in each scenario (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Travel-related CO₂ eq. emissions per patient for the current mix of in-person and digital care (“current situation”) and for the “online only” and “in person only” scenarios. The graph on the left shows data for the current travel situation, while the graph on the right shows a hypothetical travel scenario based on a shift to electric cars.

These results show that online/phone consultations can potentially generate significant reductions in CO₂ eq. by reducing the travel of patients to hospitals. For instance, if all patients adopted online / phone consultations, a reduction from 3.19 kg to 1.53 kg CO₂ eq. per patient is achievable (about 52% lower).

Considering the “full electric cars” scenario, the emissions can be further reduced by 11%, to a value of 1.36 kg CO₂ eq. per patient. It is important to note that due to increasing decarbonisation of UK electricity grid¹, the GHGs emissions from electric vehicles are expected to decrease sharply in the next years.

Our final step was to consider the CO₂ eq. impacts of the online/phone consultations. We assumed that each online/phone consultation requires 0.57 MB, which would result in emissions below 0.01 g CO₂ eq. per consultation. This is based on internet energy intensity of 0.06 kWh/GB (Aslan et al., 2018) and UK electricity grid emissions of 285 g CO₂ eq./kWh (Huijbregts et al., 2017; Wernet et al., 2016). The CO₂ eq. costs of delivering the online/phone consultations, therefore, appear negligible in comparison to the potential benefits from reduced travel.

In carrying out this case study, we encountered several challenges and limitations. A key limitation was that issues of data availability, ethics and cost made it unfeasible to account for the life cycle impacts of the technologies involved (such as patients’ and practitioners’ phones and laptops). Further research, with greater capacity to invest in these areas, is needed to gain a clearer understanding of the impacts of virtual appointments on GHG emissions and other environmental outcomes.

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¹ See e.g. [Plans unveiled to decarbonise UK power system by 2035 - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk)